

CHPM schematics and blueprints

CHPM2030 Deliverable D4.3

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CHPM2030

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CHPM2030

CHPM2030 DELIVERABLE D4.3

CHPM CHEMATICS AND BLUEPRINTS

Summary:

This deliverable is complimentary to D4.2. It contains schematics, drawings and pictures related to the technical components of the CHPM system, mainly laboratory equipment that was used by the partners for developing the technologies of the surface components for metal extraction and power generation.

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1 Introduction

The aim of the system integration work package is to combine the different processes included in the CHPM2030 project into a single system and develop a computer model for simulation of the overall metal extraction and electricity and heat production processes. The results of this work are described in deliverable D4.2 Report on CHPM process optimisation.

This deliverable (D4.3) is complimentary to D4.2. It contains schematics, drawings and pictures related to the technical components of the CHPM system, mainly laboratory equipment that was used by the partners for developing the technologies of the surface components for metal extraction and power generation.

2 Electrolytic metal recovery

Blueprints of Elevated Temperature Elevated Pressure (ETEP) – Rotating Electrode Reactor (RER) – developed by KU Leuven.

Figure 1. Process flow, Piping and Instrumentation diagram for the ETEP-RER setup. PCV - back-pressure regulator, PSV Pressure Safety Valve, MV Manual Valve, PI - Pressure Indicator, TI - Temperature Indicator, TIT – Temperature Indicator Transmitter.

Figure 2. Rotating Electrode – ETEP reactor system with control unit, with safety instruments used for estimating kinetic and transport properties of electrochemical reactions at temperatures up to 300 °C and 238 bar.

Figure 3. Schematic cross-section of (A) ETEP-RER system, with instruments, (B) ETEP Reactor, and (C) rotating electrode holder designed to operate to 300 °C and 238 bar.

Figure 5. Blueprint of ETEP – RER: Cross-section of reactor vessel.

Figure 6. Blueprint of ETEP – RER: Cross-section of reactor lid.

Figure 7. Blueprint of ETEP – RER: Cross-section of electrode holder.

3 Binary power plant and heat generation

Figure 8. Schematic diagram of a geothermal binary cycle power plant.

Figure 9. Schematic outline of geothermal CHP configurations. The red lines represent the geothermal brine.

4 Gas diffusion electro-crystallisation (GDEx)

4.1 Lab-scale GDEx reactor schematics

The blueprints for the lab-scale reactor for the GDEx process are presented in the three figures below. The construction material of the cell is PVDF, whereas the gaskets employed for sealing are made of Viton.

Figure 10. Blue prints for the anolyte and catholyte compartments (with identical specifications) of the GDEx electrochemical reactor.

Figure 11. Blue prints for the oxidant gas compartment of the GDEX electrochemical reactor.

Figure 12. Blue prints for the end-plate of the GDEX electrochemical reactor, which is placed on an appropriate reactor holder.

These blueprints conform the reactor shown below. A peristaltic pump is used for the recirculation of both the anolyte and catholyte to the corresponding compartments of the cell and the collection vessels. A volumetric flask with a column of water of 30 cm height is employed to apply an overpressure of the gas of 30 mbarg.

Figure 13. Photograph of the GDEX electrochemical reactor in operation. The labels AN, CA and air, refer to the anolyte, catholyte and gas flow circuits to the cell (white discs stacked on the right hand of the picture).

The electrochemical reactor itself contains 3 chambers. The upscaled cells to be used during the project would be based on an equivalent design of these lab-cells, with an improved flow configuration. Through the first chamber, gas (e.g., air) flows at a fixed rate, with a set overpressure, at the hydrophobic layer of the gas diffusion electrode (GDE). The hydrophilic layer of the GDE gives way to the catholyte chamber. The catholyte and anolyte flow from, and to, 3-necked glass bottles serving as reservoirs, through the respective cell compartment. The anolyte and catholyte in the cell are separated by a Zirfon® ion-permeable separator. The anode is a platinum-coated disk. Both electrodes and the separator have a projected cross section of 10 cm². The circuit is completed with a potentiostat, and a Ag/AgCl reference electrode is placed via a Luggin capillary close to the GDE.

As a working electrode, 10 cm² of VITO CORE® multi-layered carbon-based gas-diffusion cathodes were used to enable the GDEX process. The multi-layered electrodes consist of a current collector (metal gauze), an active layer made of activated carbon and a gas-diffusion layer. The current collector was made of stainless steel gauze, including a wire diameter 100 µm and mesh 44 (316L, Solana, Belgium). The composition of the hydrophilic active layer was 20% PTFE as polymer binder and 80% of activated carbon. Norit®SX1G (878 m² g⁻¹, Norit Americas Inc., USA) was employed as the active carbon source. The hydrophobic gas-diffusion outer layer was made of polytetrafluoroethylene (Teflon® PTFE 6N, Dupont). The hydrophobic particles in the hydrophobic backing were and fluorinated ethylene propylene resin (Teflon® FEP 8000, Dupont). A schematic representation of the GDE is shown in the Figure below.

Figure 14. Schematic representation of a VITO CORE® gas-diffusion electrode.

The process for electrode manufacturing at VITO is currently available to produce electrodes up to 1 m² of surface area, if needed.

4.2 Up-scaled GDEx reactor schematics

A different electrochemical cell design was employed for upscaled-experiments, wherein the main difference relies on improvements on the flow channel. A photograph of the scaled-up reactor is presented in the figure below (right) together with the electronic control unit for the potential and current (left). This reactor can be used for the processing of up to 1-10 m³ of geothermal brine within 1-10 days of operation.

Figure 15. Top: Photograph of the up-scaled GDEx electrochemical reactor in operation; left: control unit; right; electrochemical cell. Bottom: Assembly of the gas-diffusion electrode into the cell.

Further specifications of this electrochemical cell can be found in the figure presented on the following three pages, parts (A) Design overview, (B) Dimensions and (c) Assembly.

Each electrode element:

1	Electrode (1 pcs.)	8B	Outer frame sealing (1 pcs.)
2	Outer frame (1 pcs.)	10	Membrane (1 pcs.)
3	Inner frame (2 pcs.)	13	O-ring sealing for current connector (2 pcs.)
8A	In- Outlet sealing (4 pcs.)	14	Current connector (2 pcs.)

Each cell module:

a = Projected electrode area [m²] (from 0.04 to 1.04 m² in steps of 0.04 m²)

Number of electrode elements (anode plus cathode elements) = 1 + (a / 0.04)

Number of membranes (10) = a / 0.04

Number of in- Outlet sealings (8A) = 4 x (2 + (a / 0.04))

Number of outer frame sealings (8B) = 2 + (a / 0.04)

Number of O-ring sealing for current connector (13) = 2 x (1 + (a / 0.04))

(A) – Design overview

a = Projected electrode area [m²] (from 0.04 to 1.04 m² in steps of 0.04 m²)
L = 33.5 + (a x 237.5) mm ± 1%

Pipe connection:
D = 65 mm G = 1.5 inch d = 32 mm z1 = 5 mm z2 = 12 mm L1 = 23 mm L2 = 30

(B) - Dimensions

(C) - Assembly

Figure 16. Blue prints for the scaled-up GDEx electrochemical reactor shown in Figure 15. This is a specific co-design and commissioned with the company ElectroCell, to specifically fit VITO gas-diffusion electrodes. (A) Design overview. (B) Dimensions. (C) Assembly.

4.3 P&ID GDEx

Item number	V-303	P-303	E-303	V-304
Item name	Feed storage tank	Catholyte recirculation pump	GDEx reactor	Anolyte storage tank
Material of construction	Glass	PTFE	PTFE, VITO CORE® gas diffusion-electrode, Zirfon® separator	Glass
Pressure (kPa)	101	101	104	101
Temperature (°C)	15-70	15-70	15-70	15-70

Line number	3-1	3-2	3-3	3-4	3-6	3-7	3-8	3-9	3-11	3-12	3-13	3-14	3-15
Stream name	Fresh GDEx feed (e.g., geothermal brine)	O ₂ or CO ₂ or other oxidant gas	Fresh anolyte	Anolyte recirculation	Anolyte recirculation	Catholyte to centrifuge	Catholyte recirculation	Catholyte recirculation	Oxidant gas output to scrubber	Waste solution (spent brine)	Recovered solid	Waste anolyte (spent wine)	Scrubbed oxidant gas
phase	Aqueous	Gas	Aqueous	Aqueous	Aqueous	Slurry	Aqueous	Aqueous	Gas	Aqueous	Solid	Aqueous	Aqueous

Valves and instrumentation

X – Valve

AT – Catholyte pH transmitter

AI – Catholyte pH inducer

ASH – Catholyte pH high switch

IT – Current transmitter

II – Current indicator

ISH – Current high switch

FT – Oxidant gas flow-transmitter

FIC – Oxidant gas flow controller

Figure 17. P&ID of GDEX unit @VITO.

5 Salinity gradient power through reverse electro dialysis (SGP-RE) P&ID SGP-RE

5.1 P&ID SGP-RE

Figure 18. P&ID of pilot scale SGP-RE unit @VITO.

A process and instrumentation diagram is shown in Figure 18. Basically, the unit consists of three loops.

The ‘Geothermal Brine’ loop and the ‘Surface water’ circulation loop are identical and consist each of:

- Polycarbonate transparent buffer tank of 30L equipped with a vertical stirrer, low level sensor and pressure measurement for measuring liquid level in tank.
- In-line filter 500µm for protection of pumps
- Centrifugal pump: Iwaki magnetically coupled pump MDH-400CV5-D
- Peristaltic pump: WATSON MARLOW®604U
- By-pass system with rotameter flow reading to reduce flow to stack
- Flow measurement: Yokogawa AE105MG 08FT1.010
- Conductivity and temperature measurement on inlet of stack: Mettler Toledo
- Pressure measurement on inlet of stack
- Pressure measurement on outlet of stack

- Conductivity and temperature measurement on outlet of stack: Mettler Toledo

The 'Electrolyte' circulation loop consists of:

- Polycarbonate transparent buffer tank of 30L equipped with a vertical stirrer, low level sensor and pressure measurement for measuring liquid level in tank.
- In-line filter 500µm for protection of pumps
- centrifugal pump: Iwaki pump MDH-400CV5-D
- peristaltic pump: Watson-Marlow
- By-pass system with rotameter flow reading to reduce flow to stack
- Flow measurement: Yokogawa AE105MG 08FT1.010
- Conductivity and temperature measurement on inlet of stack: Mettler Toledo
- Pressure measurement on inlet of stack
- Conductivity and temperature measurement on outlet of stack: Mettler Toledo
- pH measurement KNICK Inpro 4850i (necessary when using pH-sensitive redox couple)

The whole setup is also equipped with a heating system that can heat up the fluids in the three loops to 50°C.

In an SGP-RE system each stack operates at its maximum power output when the external load matches the internal resistance of the stack. At that point 50% efficiency is achieved, which means that 50% of the available chemical potential in the brine is converted into electrical energy, 50% is lost inside the battery as Ohmic (and to a lesser extent non-Ohmic) losses. To increase the efficiency, the external load should be higher than the internal resistance of the stack. This would decrease the power output and current to the benefit of an increased efficiency.

To achieve high brine utilization at maximum power output, multiple stacks should be combined. The brine outlet of each stack should be coupled to the inlet of the next one and every stack should be supplied with the same fresh water source as shown in Figure 19. By changing the load in the external circuit, each of these stacks can be operated at maximum power output of at maximum efficiency.

Figure 19. Stacks in series for optimal power production of geothermal brine and surface water.

5.2 SGP-RE SGP-RE stack design

For CHPM2030 a specific stack design was created as shown in the following figures. The 3D drawings show the entire stack. Figure 20 and Figure 21 show a 2D drawing of the gaskets. From this drawing it can be easily understood that the path length is 148mm and the stack width is 560mm (2 times 260mm). This stack is designed for a maximal power output in terms of power density. The short path length assures that only approx. 10% of the salinity is transferred, keeping the driving force high, hence high power density can be achieved. Very specific to this stack design are the shape and position of the in- and outlets. They provide least resistance in terms of hydrodynamic flow, while still distributing very well the fluids across the total area of the spacer (separating the two membranes).

Figure 20. 2D drawing of the insets A and B in Figure 3.

Figure 21. 2D drawing of the insets A and B in Figure 20.

Figure 22. 3D drawings of the SG-RE stack, assembled and exploded view.

Figure 23. Stack assembly with 50 cell pairs and coupling to the SGP-RE pilot.

The central yellow element in Figure 22 is the membrane pile, consisting of gaskets (cf. Figure 20) spacer material and cation and anion exchange membranes. The outer part of the stack consists of (from outside to inside):

- Pressure plates: in order tightly screw all parts together in an even way
- Collector frames for the high and low salinity feed streams
- A frame for electrical connections to the electrode
- The electrode compartment

Figure 23 shows the actual assembly of the stack in the shop. The top pictures show the plates or outer parts from one side of the stack and a few assembled cell pairs on top of that. The white gaskets are clearly visible as well as the spacer (netting) material inside the gasket. The middle picture shows the completion of 50 cell pairs (20 μ m membranes in this cases). The bottom picture shows how the completed stack looks like as it is rigged to the SGP-RE pilot.